

The Path of Rural Culture into Primary School Chinese Reading Teaching

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Abstract:

Chinese is a subject with the unity of "instrumentality" and "humanity", and the "humanity" of Chinese coincides with the value of local culture. Therefore, to highlight the local culture, reshape the social ethics and inherit the excellent cultural customs, it is necessary to carry out Chinese classroom teaching, excavate Chinese teaching materials and extracurricular practice activities. In this process, internal and external forces are formed to effectively carry out Chinese teaching.

Key words: rural culture; Primary school Chinese; reading instruction

1、 The connotation of rural culture

To understand the culture of rural sages, we must first clarify the connotation of the culture of rural sages. Local culture is an important part of traditional culture, rooted in the rural soil, and absorbs the essence of excellent culture in the process of forming, thus forming its unique character. In the Chinese dictionary, rural refers to "the person whose moral character and talent are respected and respected by the villagers". Therefore, it can be seen that the culture of rural has the characteristics of locality, morality and reality in essence. First of all, the locality of rural culture is reflected in that rural culture is produced in a specific cultural soil, which is a cultural system produced by local people's long-term infiltration. Different regions have different values, so rural culture is recognized and respected by local people. Secondly, rural culture has unique morality. From the connotation of rural culture, we can see that only noble morality and being respected can become the representative of rural. Therefore, rural culture has the function of cultivating human nature in the process of its emergence. Finally, the culture of rural sages is realistic, mainly in serving the reality and promoting the local development. The educational value of rural sage's culture echoes with the socialist core values, which plays an important role in implementing the spirit of the socialist core values. Not only that, the culture of rural sages can make future generations remember nostalgia, stimulate local feelings, and love their hometown, Contribute to the development of my hometown. To sum up, rural culture is a unique "grassroots culture" rooted in the excellent traditional Chinese culture, which has great expansion and penetration. However, rural culture needs to be vigorously promoted and developed, and Chinese has a unique "humanity", so it is the most powerful and convenient way to integrate rural culture into Chinese teaching.

2、 Multi-dimensional value of the integration of rural culture into Chinese Reading Teaching in primary schools

Rural culture is an indispensable part of Chinese excellent traditional culture, which has the value of highlighting the local culture, reshaping social ethics and inheriting excellent cultural customs.

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(1) Highlight local culture

Culture rooted in people's production and life, through continuous refinement and the formation of invisible values. At the same time, culture is a country's "soft power". How to enhance the country's "soft power", we need to enter from the countryside, we need to start from the local culture. And the local culture is a kind of culture produced in a specific region, which plays an auxiliary role in the Rural Revitalization Strategy. Not only that, it can also show the local culture incisively and vividly, so as to better understand the local culture. With the trend of globalization, cultural pluralism leads to the collision between cultures, so students are more exposed to foreign culture and ignore the local culture. The culture of rural sages is a special form of culture. From the local characteristics of rural sages' culture, it can be seen that rural sage's culture is mainly presented around local people and things, which is in line with the subjective standards and expectations of local people. It can be generally recognized and respected by people, better highlight the local culture, and reshape the style of local culture. Secondly, the local culture elements can be well integrated, the scattered customs can be presented in the way of culture, and infiltrated into the Chinese classroom teaching, so as to achieve the effect of moistening things silently. In the teaching process, we can remember the hometown, remember the nostalgia, tell the story of our hometown, inherit the culture of our hometown, and contribute to the construction of our hometown.

(2) Remolding social ethics

Social moral standards need to be observed by everyone. Today's rural culture and socialist core values coincide. The reason is that the characteristic of rural culture is morality. First of all, because of its special character of educating people, the research scope is not limited to people, but also focuses on the outstanding contributions made by local sages. At the same time, more attention is paid to the ideological and moral character and moral sentiment of local sages. Secondly, the development of rural culture is inseparable from the continuous evolution of society, which can be developed into an important source of socialist core values. Therefore, the ultimate goal of "patriotism, dedication, honesty and friendliness" in the socialist core values is exactly the same. Therefore, the inheritance of rural culture is essentially to promote the implementation of socialist core values in the local. Finally, because of its unique local characteristics, the local culture has a far-reaching influence. The local culture has played an auxiliary role in the continuous promotion of the socialist core values, making the socialist core values "take root" and playing a significant role in reshaping the social ethics. Primary school students are in the critical stage of moral cognition. Therefore, the introduction of rural culture into primary school Chinese teaching can arouse students' emotional resonance while telling celebrity stories. Not only that, it can also maintain the rural historical memory, stimulate students' love for the countryside, and enhance the collective consciousness.

(3) Inheriting excellent cultural customs

The traditional Chinese culture needs to be inherited and developed, and the culture of local sages can be used as an entry point. Recently, the Ministry of education has issued the textbook guide for the introduction of Chinese excellent traditional culture into primary and secondary schools, which indicates that it is essential to infiltrate Chinese excellent culture into teaching activities. In today's world, intercultural communication leads to the coexistence of cultural diversity. In this context, the channels for students to contact with Chinese excellent traditional culture are more narrow, which leads to the further strengthening of contemporary students' understanding of Chinese excellent traditional culture. The construction of Chinese excellent traditional culture is inseparable from the local people's vigorous promotion of the local culture. Therefore, the inheritance and development of excellent cultural customs can start from the local culture. At the same time of inheriting excellent cultural customs, the study of rural culture can also cultivate inheritors. For a long time, China's one-way flow of population from the countryside into the city, which is also an important reason for the "fracture surface" of rural culture. Since the implementation of the Rural

Revitalization Strategy, many people have returned to their hometown for employment and entrepreneurship, injecting new vitality into the culture of rural sages, forming a "new rural sages culture". Those who have returned to build their hometown are "new rural sages", and they are also one of the main bodies of Chinese excellent cultural heritage. Therefore, the infiltration of local culture in Chinese teaching has a dual role, in the inheritance of excellent cultural customs at the same time; it can cultivate the main body of inheritance.

3、 The path of rural culture into primary school Chinese Reading Teaching

There are three ways to integrate the rural culture into the primary school Chinese Reading Teaching: tamping the students' Chinese literacy in the classroom teaching, excavating the rural culture in the teaching materials in order to shorten the distance with the students, and inheriting the rural culture in the extracurricular practical activities.

(1) Classroom teaching -- strengthening Chinese quality

It is the most direct way to infiltrate the local culture into the primary school Chinese reading teaching. The classroom is the main position for students to learn knowledge and experience culture. By introducing the local culture into the classroom teaching activities, students can actively absorb cultural knowledge in the rich classroom atmosphere, and the cultural knowledge contained in the classroom is internalized into students' own knowledge. Therefore, teachers should make good use of classroom time, take the local culture as the fulcrum of classroom teaching, and carefully design a variety of classroom teaching activities. It not only improves the effect of Chinese classroom, but also improves students' Chinese literacy. When teaching "Yan'an, I'll pursue you", teachers can combine the local culture of local sages and excavate the red spirit in the local culture of sages. Students can experience the patriotic atmosphere personally, so as to stimulate their patriotic feelings. Therefore, students can independently check the local patriotic figures and related patriotic events in advance, and exchange and share in the classroom. While cultivating students' communication, sharing and cooperation, they can also skillfully integrate the local culture. The integration of rural culture into primary school Chinese reading teaching is not only to improve the effectiveness of teaching and make the classroom more rich and vivid, but also to better implement the "humanity" of Chinese. In the process of Chinese learning, students can experience the uniqueness of local rural culture and constantly consolidate their Chinese literacy.

(2) Mining teaching materials -- shortening the distance between texts

Teaching materials are the basis of learning, and also the carrier of local culture. Since 2017, primary and secondary schools in China have used the textbooks compiled by the Ministry of education, and the textbooks used this time are about traditional culture. At the same time, they can make students "zero distance contact" with the textbooks, and truly experience the combination of learning and life. At present, many teachers attach importance to imparting knowledge in Chinese teaching, but ignore the humanity of Chinese education. Therefore, teachers should attach importance to the excellent traditional culture contained in primary school Chinese teaching materials and excavate the humanistic elements in the teaching materials. In order to shorten the distance between students and text in Chinese teaching, teachers must base on the teaching materials and excavate the cultural significance. Therefore, when preparing lessons, teachers should combine the wisdom of local culture with the content of teaching materials to shorten the distance between students and the text. For the third grade students, Chinese traditional culture can't clearly define its meaning. Moreover, due to the vast territory of our country, the customs of different places are very different. Therefore, when designing the teaching of ancient poem Yuanri, teachers can integrate the local customs of Spring Festival with the Spring Festival scenes described in the ancient poem, so as to shorten the text distance for students to discuss. At the same time, it can also expand the customs of the Dragon Boat Festival and Qingming Festival, and find the excellent traditional culture of the Chinese nation in these traditional customs. In this process, on the one hand, it can arouse students' empathy; on the

other hand, it can improve students' enthusiasm in learning Chinese.

(3) Extracurricular practice -- inheriting the local culture

The organic combination of national curriculum, local curriculum and school-based curriculum is the curriculum implementation mode advocated by our country since the implementation of curriculum reform. The organic infiltration of rural culture into primary school Chinese teaching is the best way to further develop and expand school-based curriculum, as well as to expand students' extracurricular practice and inherit rural culture. Although Chinese classroom teaching is the main position of students' learning, due to the limited classroom time, we should also extend the local culture to extracurricular practice, and carry out extracurricular practice activities related to the local culture. For example, when teaching the text Huang Jiguang, teachers can hold a speech contest about "revolutionary martyrs" to encourage students to participate actively and enhance their national pride. Moreover, we can organize students to participate in research and study tours, mainly to visit the local red revolutionary base, in combination with the activities of "the 100th anniversary of the founding of the Communist Party of China". In the process of research, students can not only experience the feelings of home and country, but also play an important role in the inheritance of local culture. Therefore, as an excellent Chinese teacher, in order to better infiltrate the local culture in Chinese teaching, we must strengthen the design of extracurricular practice activities, form internal and external forces, further strengthen students' familiarity with local culture, build a good bridge between Chinese extracurricular practice and local culture, stimulate students' love for their hometown, and remember nostalgia, Tell a good story about your hometown.

In primary school, as a Chinese teacher, we should actively combine the local culture with Chinese teaching, seek the conjunction with local culture based on classroom, teaching materials and extracurricular practice, infiltrate the excellent local culture into classroom teaching, help students establish correct outlook on life and values, and improve their cultural self-cultivation, Lay the foundation for the future development of students.

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